

HISTORICAL INFORMATION ON THE LINGUISTIC AND LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF PLACE NAMES

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***Abstract.** The issues of linguoculturology, related to the understanding of language and culture, which are of great interest in world linguistics, are being studied by many researchers and are being investigated as a new area of modern linguistics. The rapid development of the world community, integration and mixing of cultures, globalization, scientific contacts, all of which are associated with the communicative process, make the study of the languages and cultures of different peoples, comparative research, and solving the problems of world linguistics an urgent task in every respect.*

***Keywords:** toponymic units, toponyms, study of vocabulary, modern English language, history, linguistic value of toponyms.*

Studying the vocabulary of modern English is one of the important components of modern linguistics. Studying the word-formation system of modern English makes it possible to determine the rules and patterns of construction and formation of new words. The ability to isolate word-formation elements in a word, determine the method of its formation and the word-formation model by which it is created, contributes to the conscious and deep assimilation of lexical units of the language and, as a rule, a higher level of mastery of English or another foreign language. The word-formation system of English language is a single whole, the individual elements of which, depending on the need, are more or less actively and differently used to create new lexical units. In our study, toponyms are understood as geographical names of any, from large to small, natural or artificially created by man objects on the land or water territory of the Earth, forming historically, socially and culturally determined geographical names. "The main word-formation processes include affixation (prefixation, suffixation), root formation, borrowing, compounding, stable phrases, semantic word formation, formation of proper names from common nouns, abbreviations, conversion"[4].

A distinction is made between synchronic and diachronic word formation. Diachronic word formation studies the actual processes of formation of some linguistic signs from others throughout the historical development of language, as well as historical changes in the word-formation structure of individual words (in particular, through simplification and re-decomposition). Synchronic word formation studies not so much processes as relationships between words coexisting in one synchronic section of language.

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the form Bensintona, in 1217 Basington, in 1526 Benston. The name consists of three components: the proper name Baenesa, the possessive suffix -ing, -tūn "estate, farm", that is, "the estate of Benesa" [7]. In the process of development of the name, the suffix of possession was lost, and then contraction occurred, which led to the loss of the etymological motivation of the components of the complex toponym. Thus, when examined synchronically, the structure of a geographical name differs and requires additional examination in the diachronic plane, where the name is complex. V.D. Belenkaya understands motivation in the synchronic aspect as "the semantic structure of a toponym, its internal form, that is, the morphological properties that are actually perceived by members of a given group." [6] However, for residents of England, the problem of motivation of names does not exist, since most of the toponyms of this country remain stable.

When new names appear, they are perceived as motivated, since they are traditional, regardless of their correspondence or non-correspondence to the object's features and etymological meaning. A significant role in the synchronic study of toponymic systems is played by the analysis of geographical terms in geographical names. In foreign and domestic linguistics, toponyms and toponym bases are distinguished, which are the constituent components of a toponym. A toponym is understood as a service component that participates in the formation of a toponym. A toponymic base is a semantic element of a geographical name, despite the fact that its meaning may be lost in a modern language. According to N.V. Podolskaya, "each language has a certain set of its own typical toponymic bases; moreover, each more or less isolated territory, toponymic zone, has its own set, different from others, which is due to a number of reasons, including geographical and ethnographic realities and dialectisms [3]. It is obvious that sometimes it is difficult to determine the composition of a geographical name, since toponyms can be of different origins. The studied material shows that some components of English names are former geographical terms that are part of a proper name. Most English toponyms are phrases. A certain term reflecting the real properties of the above-mentioned object, i.e. its features or parameters, can be put forward as a key morpheme of a given toponym model. Great Britain and English language have undergone successive waves of immigrants. Let us consider the toponymic historical layers of this territory in chronological order: a) the Celtic toponymic layer; b) Latin elements; c) the Anglo-Saxon toponymic layer; d) Scandinavian elements; d) French elements. Toponymic layers are a historical category, i.e. changing. The reason for these changes may be migration processes. But regardless of how radically toponyms change, the names of previous eras are preserved alongside the new ones [Sudar 2004:75].

Celtic toponymic layer. Long before the Roman conquests, many rivers and hills received their names from British tribes. The oldest names of England that have survived to this day belong to the Celtic language.

The Celts, who were representatives of the Indo-European culture, are believed to have settled on the British Isles about 2,500 years ago. In the early 11th century BC, the invasion of Britain and its subsequent settlement by Celtic tribes began, which continued until the 1st century BC. The Celts mixed with the Scots and Picts living in this territory, and the mixed population, mainly of Celtic origin, is traditionally called the Britons. Close contacts between representatives of different cultures affected the mutual penetration of one language into another. The geography of the settlement of the Celts can be traced thanks to the regularly repeating component wal- (Old English *walh*, *walas* "Britons"), which indicates the location of the Celtic population after the arrival of the Anglo-Saxons in the 6th century and the possible preservation of Celtic elements.

For example, the name Walcot Farm, "home of the Britons", may indicate that the area was inhabited by Celts[9-10].

The earlier inhabitants spoke an unknown "non-Indo-European" language. No written sources have survived, so the attempts of scholars to attribute the language of the first settlers of the British Isles to proto-Basque, proto-Berber, Euro-African, Phoenician, and even the language of the tribes living at the North Pole have been futile. There are a huge number of names, mainly river names, that cannot be attributed to any language, so they are attributed to an extinct, ancient language. For example, the name of the Gihl River (the modern Ray River) is attributed to an unknown pre-Celtic language, although the Swedish linguist E. Ekwall finds similarities with the Welsh word *iaith* (literal translation "language") "talkative stream" [9]. It is typical for England as a whole to use in the names of settlements not only terms denoting settlements, but to a greater extent term that, by their semantics, relate to natural geographical objects.

"Celtic roots are now more often found in the names of rivers, hills, and forests in the areas of late English settlement, namely Cornwall, Cumbria, Lancashire, Cheshire, Gloucestershire, and also in Ireland and Wales." [6:25-26] The city of Thame (Tame 100 AD) received its name from the Thames tributary Thame (Celtic *tam* "dark"). [6] There is an assumption that Thame means "river" in Celtic, since it is rarely called by the name of Tame at present, but is more often called the river "river".

Thus, the analysis of Celtic names revealed the main universal characteristics of toponyms - this is the use of features of the described object (sparkling, dark) and directly geographical terms in the nomination, such as a river, a hill. That is, the main function of Celtic names was orientation in space.

Latin elements. In England, traces of Latin influence are barely noticeable, despite almost 400 years of Roman domination over Britain. Julius Caesar launched two campaigns into Britain, in the 55th and 54th centuries BC, but failed. The successful conquest of England by Rome began in the 43rd century AD and was largely completed by the end of the 60s. England was one of the outlying provinces of the Roman Empire. Romanization affected mainly the southern, eastern, and partly central regions, but this did not lead to fundamental changes in Celtic society. The final element street comes from the Latin *strata*, meaning "paved road" or "Roman road". In some geographical names, the toponym street acts as the initial component. Today, only two names in England have survived that are entirely Latin: Catterick (North Yorkshire) and Speen (Berkshire) [18-19]. The remaining toponyms are Latinized forms of ancient names in a significantly modified form.

Moreover, the population of the British Isles did not speak Latin, but Breton, a Celtic language of the Indo-European language family that later split into Cornish and Welsh. Settlements, which often had market squares, developed in geographically advantageous places, such as at the intersections of several routes. Therefore, many settlements and villages have survived to this day. Apparently, their original names changed several times due to changes in ownership, but the names of church parishes and even farms go back to the distant past, and some of them even to pre-Roman times.

These settlements were founded near water sources or sheltered hills that have changed little since then. For example, the small town of Stratton Audley, "farm by the Roman road," derives from the *strata* component of the north-south Roman road Buckle Street along which it

was built. The origin of the name of the small hill Street. Hill is also related to this road, which runs close to the hill where it crosses the River Ray[16].

One of the characteristic features is the frequent use of the component *chester / caster* (Latin *castra*, OE *caster* – camp) in the names of settlements that were located on the site of former Roman fortifications and towns. Most often, this element is used with ancient determinate components of Celtic origin. Therefore, the names of this period can be called Latinized forms of Celtic names. For example, Alchester and Dorchester. Alchester is a Roman city, the first element of which is the Celtic *alauna* "white water", and the second is the Latin *ceaster* (Alencestre 1160) [14-15]. It was founded almost immediately after the Roman conquest around 50 AD, possibly as a fort.

It should not be forgotten that in the Middle Ages, Latin was the language of many official documents, so it is not surprising that a Latin word was included in a geographical name. The Anglo-Saxons borrowed a few Latin words: *castra* (camp) – *ceaster* (English) – *chester*, via *strata* – street. Maps of modern England also contain names with borrowed prepositions and adverbs. In general, most Latin names are associated with military settlements. Topographic names typical of the Roman period in England reflect the history of the construction of roads and fortified points to contain raids.

Anglo-Saxon toponymic layer. The Anglo-Saxons, who settled in England around the 5th century, in addition to their culture brought their language – Old English, which later became the basis of modern English. This name was given to the language from the beginning of English settlement around 700 - 1150, but in some cases it is also called Anglo-Saxon. [11] One of the important characteristics of Old English, in our opinion, is that it was an inflectional language, that is, it was characterized by the variability of word forms and parts of words: endings were added to nouns and verbs, which contributed to the free word-order in a sentence. Since many toponyms originate from the Anglo-Saxon period, their original form is represented by Old English. The Anglo-Saxons adopted some Celtic names of rivers and villages. When a name was borrowed, it was assimilated, that is, vowels and consonants were rendered by similar equivalents.

The toponym then developed linguistically like any other name of Anglo-Saxon origin. According to C. Cameron, the division of England into administrative parts called counties (shire) began in the Anglo-Saxon period, in the 9th – 10th centuries. Initially, the word shire meant "division of people", but soon enough this concept was used in relation to the area inhabited by people, and later in the meaning of "a unit of administrative-territorial division of the kingdom" [17].

The greatest concentration of geographical names dating back to the Anglo-Saxon period (approximately the end of the 6th - beginning of the 7th centuries) is found along the River Thames and the oldest road, the Icknield Way, which the Anglo-Saxons supposedly took from the north-east. The Anglo-Saxon layer of toponyms is reflected by the formants: *-ing* - a suffix of possession or genitive case, *ham* "dwelling, estate, village", *hampton*, *ton* "farm with outbuildings, village", *wic* "dairy farm", *borough* (*bergh*, *burh*) "fortification". The Old English names are based on the nouns: *clif*, *cumb*, *ende*, *ford*, *sand*, *thorn*, *wella*, which can be correlated with the modern words *cliff*, *hollow*, *end of an estate or district*, *ford*, *sand*, *thorn-tree*, *well*, respectively. One of the most ancient and commonly used formants in English toponymy is *-ing*, which dates back to the early period of Anglo-Saxon settlements. This patronymic suffix is used in the names of geographical objects that were named after their inhabitants or descendants of an early settler. There are several

variants of the use of the -ing formant in toponyms. In its simplest form, at the end of a name, this suffix, when attached to a proper name, denotes the son or other descendant of the person (son of, descendant of) who created the given name, that is, it is actually used as an equivalent of the genitive case. For example, the name of Alfred the Great is found in documents in the form Ælfred Æpelwulfing Alfred, son of Ethelwulf [12-14]. At the end of the 5th century, England was divided into three barbarian kingdoms - the kingdom of the Angles, the kingdom of the Saxons and the kingdom of the Jutes (Kent), each of which was founded by chieftains who initially led the first settlers or tribes and established themselves as kings. The earliest English place names also include those indicating places where the Angles, Saxons and Jutes worshipped pagan deities.

These geographical names can be divided into three groups. The first group includes names denoting pagan temples or tombs. The second group includes names of worship centers, places dedicated to certain deities. The last group includes names that indicate the existence of a sacrificial ritual. The Old English element wīg "pagan temple" is found in Wyfold, where the final element fold is "church, bosom of the church"[18]. Other names denote centers of worship of certain gods or goddesses. For example, Thunor is the god of thunder and storm, corresponding to the Scandinavian Thor, in the name Taston —Thor's stonell - "Thor's stone" refers to the monolith, which is located in the village and was considered the arrow of this deity. Mythological animals and spirits occupy a significant place in the toponymy of England. Some names of fields and hills reflect belief in supernatural beings, such as elves, goblins, giants, gnomes, dragons. The latter, according to legend, were the guardians of treasures. Near the village of Garsington there is a field called Drakenhord —dragon's hoardll – "dragon's hoard", the name of which was supposedly given based on the items found in the mound. Another name Brokenberue —broken be(o)rgll – "ruined mountain", located in the same area, can serve as evidence of this. In the adjacent administrative district of Baldon there is another field, the name of which mentions a dragon, Drakestone —dragon stonell – "dragon stone". The hills and mountains were considered to be the habitat of elves and goblins. For example, Poppets Hill —pit haunted by goblinsll or Elvendon —hill haunted by elvesll. The Anglo-Saxons believed in giants who protected reservoirs and dwarves who infested valleys and forests: Tusmore —giant's poolll; Thomley —woodland clearing haunted by dwarvesll[22].

The toponymy also reflects the process of Christianization of the country in the Anglo-Saxon period, which is impossible to imagine without missionary activity. The name Berinsfield represents the name of Bishop St. Birinius. The toponyms of the studied period contain names of the natural landscape, emphasizing individual characteristics of geographical objects. In this regard, high productivity and diversity of geographical terms for the following realities is noted: valley (-bottom, -coombe, -denu, -slæd), stream (-æwelm, -broc, -ea, -lacu, -rith, -rithig, -spring, -welle), hill (- beorg, Clif-, -cliff(e), -dūn, -hill, -hlāw, -ness) and others. This unique feature is characteristic of Anglo-Saxon toponymy, as opposed to modern English, which uses fewer words to describe natural features.

Scandinavian elements. The earliest names of Viking settlements in England, which included Danes and Norwegians, are noted in the Anglo-Saxon Chronicle in the chronicle entry for 876, when a Danish army settled in Northumbria[21].

Traces of Scandinavian influence (9th – 11th centuries) in toponymy can be found in the territory of the former Scandinavian possessions, collectively called Danelaw (literally "Danish law") - an area of Danish law that covers the counties of Yorkshire, Lincolnshire, Norfolk,

Leicestershire, Nottinghamshire, Lancashire, Westmorland, Cumberland. In the southern part of Danelaw, the Old English dialect was subject to Scandinavian influence. The foundation of Scandinavian settlements led to the formation of a Scandinavian toponymic background. Old Norse and Old English did not deviate much from Germanic, and many words in the vocabulary of these two languages were similar or close in meaning. However, in those areas where the Danes dominated, the peculiarities of their speech left their mark on geographical names. K. Cameron notes that *thorp* is a distinctly Danish word and its wide use in England, a country of small villages and farms, is not surprising [Cameron 1977:78]. The Scandinavians brought with them a set of personal names that were used for the names of villages and secondary settlements. In many names, the proper name was the first element of the toponym, and the geographical term was the second: Dunthorp "settlement of Dunn". The Scandinavians, like the Anglo-Saxons, used a similar naming system. The modern formant *-bourne* "spring, key, brook" in English toponymy was established by the Danes through the introduction of the Scandinavian word *brunnr*. For example, the names of fields come from the brook that flowed near these objects: East Hagbourne, West Hagbourne. Thus, the Scandinavian influence on geographical names is very insignificant. Despite the predominant distribution of Danish names in the Danelaw area, several toponyms with the stable element *-thorp* can be found in northwest Oxfordshire, which once again emphasizes the expansion of Danish borders through the emergence of new colonies[21].

This is evidenced by the names themselves, indicating the exact location of settlements. A small number of Danish components function in simple, compound and conditionally-articulated names.

French elements. In 1066, the Norman conquerors who came from France preserved the cultural and linguistic traditions of this country. However, despite the significant socio-cultural influence of the Norman conquest, this did not lead to the emergence of an extensive French toponymic layer. It is important to remember that this layer of names does not include names that originated in or contain French words that later became an integral part of the Middle English vocabulary. French was the official language of high society for the next two centuries, but its influence on the toponymy of England is subtle and does not reach a high concentration in any area. The transfer of toponyms from France, observed during the Norman Conquest, was often accompanied by a change in the pronunciation of French names. The influence of the French language on the toponyms of England is clearly seen in the names of monasteries and castles. These names were transferred directly from France: Rewley Abbey "royal place". The name is a dedication and serves as a reminder of the founder of the monastery, Richard, brother of Henry III. The name of the pavement in Oxford Grandpont "great bridge" - "large bridge" consists of two components, where the word *bridge* implies a paved pavement crossing ditches and streams.

After the Grandpont, another bridge appeared in the city with the French name *Pettypont* "little bridge". One example of the influence of the Anglo-Norman language in place names is the representation of the Old English *c* before *e* or *i*. For example, in the word *ceaster*, the initial *c* is represented in Modern English by the combination *ch*. This sound was not found in Norman, where in such cases *c* was pronounced as a combination *ts*, and later *s*, although in writing it was represented by the letter *c*. Anglo-Norman spelling and pronunciation has been preserved in some place names containing the word *ceaster*: Alcester, Worcester College. Another example of sound substitution is the Norman *T* instead of the initial English digraph *Th*, which was absent in the Anglo-Norman language: Tusmore "giant's pool" - "enormous pool". In addition to proper and

descriptive names, the toponymy of this period reflects several aspects of medieval life, one of which is hunting. The wooded area (Wychwood, Woodstock, Shotover, Stowood forests) of the county with its rich fauna attracted the late kings of Normandy and the early representatives of the Angevin royal dynasty of Plantagenets. The name of the field Purrance (Purveance) means providing provisions for the royal house during a visit to Wychwood Forest. Tournaments were common in the Angevin period, as indicated by the open hilly area of Baynard's Green, where Bayard is the name of a bay horse, which is also found in the name Bayswater Brook (Bayard's Watering place) [23].

Observations show that the geographical names of the Norman period have a tendency towards possessive names, descriptive, highlighting the objective feature of the object, and reflecting the lifestyle of that time. The result of the Norman conquest was the displacement of the Old English language and, accordingly, some significant changes in the spelling and pronunciation of already existing geographical names. The toponymic system of England, which developed historically, is heterogeneous and combines materials from several languages from different historical eras. The toponymic picture of the world embodies the character of the culture of each nation and each person. Description, analysis and comparison of cultural and historical information contained in geographical names of a particular country belongs to linguistics. Within the framework of this science, a toponym begins to act as a word containing data on culture, history and, of course, language. We believe that the results of toponym research will help to increase students' interest in studying the language and culture of England and expand their knowledge in the field of history and geography. To introduce students to toponyms, we chose the work of J.R.R. Tolkien "The Lord of the Rings", since the author himself wrote "A Guide to Proper Names in The Lord of the Rings" for translators [J.R. R. Tolkien. Guide to the Names in The Lord of the Rings]. This circumstance will allow students to understand the translation of geographical names from the inside, from the position of the author, and will also allow them to better feel the origin of toponyms.

According to A.E. Mamatov, the solution of specific problems of the relationship between language and culture by linguoculturology can be carried out in two directions. On the one hand, linguoculturology studies the influence of the cultural factor on language (problems of cultural linguistics), on the other hand, the influence of the language factor on culture (problems of linguistic culturology). However, the object of linguoculturology, in their relationship to each other, should consist of language and culture. Such an idea of the integrity of the object of research makes it possible to solve a complex of problems on the basis of a single scientific-theoretical approach. According to D.U. Ashurova[3], the relationship between language and culture is most clearly expressed in literary texts. A literary text, first presented, contains socio-cultural, aesthetic, and emotional information.

R. U. Madjidova[9-10], in her research paper "Axiological study of anthropocentric articles (based on materials from Uzbek and Russian languages)," analyzed anthropocentric articles as an integral part of the anthropomorphic cultural fund. The scientist emphasizes that articles arise on the basis of human values and national-cultural characteristics. Also, the research analyzes the culture of Uzbek and Russian people, as reflected in the articles. [11]. The so-called linguocultural units, namely the national realities that emerge at the intersection of language and culture, are distinguished by the fact that their content and essence encompass national cultural concepts.

It should be emphasized that today, as part of linguocultural studies, scientific and methodological research related to the concept of linguoculturalism is being conducted both in the field of linguistics and in the field of education. They can be grouped as follows: • linguocultural studies of linguistics, which study a certain type of linguocultural features from the point of view of toponymy, animalistics, somatisms, anthroponyms, phraseological expressions and stable combinations, kinship terms, and are carried out from the perspective of classification; • Linguocultural studies on language learning, which are based on the study of the use of linguocultural elements in speech, priority criteria arising from the mentality of speakers in the speech act, speech patterns, and verbal and nonverbal means, the use of which requires consistency in the process of communication with speakers in various speech situations. We can also include lacunae, realities, stereotypes, paremiological studies, customs and traditions in the list of linguocultural units. It is in English and Uzbek languages under study that we aimed to shed light on the connection of the names of equipment with national culture and past values. We will analyze the names of household equipment within each linguistic and cultural unit. Realia (Latin) means “real” - “material”, “real things”, and means things that exist in existence, unlike abstract concepts. The main feature that distinguishes realia from other related concepts is that they have the meaning of an object-thing.

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